
The Effect of Earning Per Share and Cash Flow of Operating on Stock Prices

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ABSTRACT

The company is an entity that aims to seek profit for the welfare of the owner. Achieving company profits requires resources in carrying out its business processes. One of the resources that companies really need is funds. Companies can raise funds in various ways, one of which is by issuing securities such as shares on the stock exchange. Stock is an investment that has a big risk so that investors need to consider more to invest in stocks, one of which is by considering the earnings per share and the company's cash earning ability in the company's main activities. So as to know the effect of earnings per share and operating cash flow on stock prices. If earnings per share and operating cash flow are attractive to investors, the demand for shares in the company will increase, causing share prices to rise. Therefore, a regression test is conducted to determine the effect of earnings per share and operating cash flow on stock prices, the results are that earnings per share and operating cash flow have a significant effect on stock prices, these results are supported by previous research results which has the same test result.

1. INTRODUCTION

The company is an entity founded with the aim of making the owner prosperous. The company has the goal of getting as much profit as possible by all means, various strategies will be implemented in order to get more profit, of course, by following and not contradicting applicable rules and laws. Implementing a strategic plan requires various preparations, especially in funding. (Kustono et al. 2021). Company funding can be obtained in various ways. Companies can run a company with internal funds, namely funds obtained from company profits and owner's capital, but large companies certainly need large amounts of funds to run them because companies need more funds than internal funds. (Wbba and Pratomo). Companies can seek outside funding or external

funds by issuing stocks, bonds and other securities.(Fawaid Ridwan and Supian 2021).

In contrast to bonds, which receive funds from other parties without sharing ownership, issuing shares means that the company shares its ownership with other parties and the company has an obligation to share its profits in the form of dividends to shareholders. (Paramita et al. 2020). Dividend distribution is determined by company policy, the company can distribute dividends in the form of cash or shares. Shareholders will receive dividends indefinitely until the share owners release their shares.(Gumanti et al. 2020).

Although stocks promise dividends indefinitely, stocks carry a high risk. Investors need a lot of consideration before investing in stocks.(Putra et al.). In investing, especially in stock investment, investors will minimize their investment risk by using information from

financial reports before investing. In the financial statements, there is data that can be processed to help investors make investment decisions. (Agustin et al. 2021). One of the data in the financial statements that can be used as a judgment is earnings per share and cash flow. (Winarno et al. 2021). Cash flow consists of three activities, namely operating, investing, and financing activities. (Atmadja et al. 2019). Cash flow which is the result of the company's main activities is cash flow from operating activities so that investors can consider the company's ability to generate cash from the company's main activities. (Sumani et al. 2021). This study was conducted to find out the relationship between the data in the financial statements in the form of earnings per share and the cash flow component in the form of cash flow from operating activities to stock prices. (Dewantara et al. 2021).

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES

Earnings per Share

Earnings per share is net income minus dividends (profit available to common stockholders) divided by the weighted average number of ordinary shares outstanding which will result in earnings per share (Badruzaman 2017). So that from these data investors can find out how much profit they get from each share. (KUSTONO 2019).

Earnings per share (EPS) can be used as an indicator to assess the company in getting profits to be distributed to shareholders. (Sih et al. 2019). Potential investors can consider EPS before investing in shares in a company. (Wicaksono et al. 2021)

Cash Flow

The company's cash flow can come from three activities, namely cash flow from operating activities, cash flow from investing activities, and cash flow from financing activities. (Ana et al. 2021). The cash flows from these three activities reflect the company's cash outflows and cash inflows in one period. The total cash flow can be in the form of an increase or decrease in the company's cash flow in one period. (Andreas et al. 2020).

Investors will be interested in investing if the company has good cash flow, so that cash flow information can be used as a consideration in investing (Nurmalasari and Yulianto 2015). The objective of investing is to make a profit, which can be in the form of cash obtained by

investors from the investee company. So that the company's ability to generate cash will greatly affect the payment of obligations to investors, especially the payment of cash dividends to shareholders. (Farida et al. 2019).

Stock Prices

Shares Is proof of ownership of a company in which the owners are known as shareholders. (Krishnatama et al. 2019). The party that carries out the operation and provision of systems and / or facilities for buying and selling securities is the stock exchange. (Kustono 2020). Sale and purchase of securities through the stock exchange, so that a person or party is recognized as a shareholder if that person or party has been written on the Shareholders Register (DPS) (Adiliawan 2010).

Shares have a nominal value stated on the shares. The nominal value of shares with the share price in the market is a different matter. The value used in buying and selling shares is the stock market price. (Paramita et al. 2020a). Market price is the price currently prevailing in the market. Stock prices fluctuate influenced by many factors, so the stock price is presented every day based on the closing price on the exchange on the day concerned. (Rachmi et al. 2020).

Hypothesis

1. Earnings Per Share
 - H0: EPS does not have a significant effect on stock prices
 - H1: EPS has a significant effect on stock prices
2. Cash Flow from Operating Activities
 - H0: Cash flow from operating activities does not have a significant effect on stock prices
 - H1: Cash flows from operating activities have a significant effect on stock prices

3. RESEARCH METHOD

The data used in this study are secondary data obtained from the company's financial statements. (Prihatini et al. 2019). The data obtained from the company's financial statements is data on the company's earnings per share or earnings per share and changes in the company's cash in 2018 and 2019 for the independent variable and data on the closing share price of the company in 2018 and 2019 for the dependent variable. (Miqdad and Oktaviani 2021).

The population of this study are companies listed on the Indonesia Stock

Exchange (IDX) engaged in various industrial sectors. While the sample taken is 16 companies from the population.(Krishnatama et al. 2019). The data collection method used by researchers is the documentation method, namely by collecting statistical data from financial report documents and from stock prices.(Kuncorowati et al. 2021).

Research variables are independent and dependent variables. The independent variable of this study is earnings per share and changes in company cash in 2018 and 2019, while the dependent variable of this study is the company's stock price at the close of 2018 and 2019.(Krishnatama et al. 2019).

Testing Data

Because the test uses secondary data, a classic test is needed. Before the classical test is carried out, a data normality test must be carried out which results if it passes it can be continued with the classical assumption test.(Rachmi et al. 2020).

Normality test

The normality test used in this study was the One Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov using a significance level of 0.05.

Classic assumption test

Multicollinearity test

The multicollinearity test can be used to determine the multicollinearity symptoms in the data. If there are symptoms of multicollinearity, the regression coefficient cannot be determined, and the standard deviation becomes infinite (Setiawan and Tjun 2010). For this reason, multicollinearity testing can be done by looking at the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value found in the Coefficients (α) table, Multicollinearity Statistics column. In addition, it can also be seen from the Tolerance value in the same column. (Anon.). The limit for Tolerance is 0.01 and the limit for the VIF value must be less than 10. Where:

- Tolerance value <0.01 or $VIF > 10$ = multicollinearity occurs.
- Tolerance value > 0.01 or $VIF < 10$ = no multicollinearity occurred.

Autocorrelation test

The autocorrelation test aims to determine whether there is a correlation between the confounding variable in a certain period and the disturbing variable in the previous period (Setiawan and Tjun 2010),namely by evaluating

the value of Durbin Watson (DW). This multiple linear regression model will be free from autocorrelation if the calculated DW value approaches the number two (2) or falls into the 5 Durbin Watson criteria. (Paramita et al. 2020b).

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test is used to determine whether there are deviations from the classic heteroscedasticity assumption, namely the inequality of variants of the residuals for all observations in the regression model. (Putra and Prabowo 2019). Regression cannot be fulfilled if there are symptoms of heteroscedasticity. In this study, the heteroscedasticity test will be carried out using the Scatterplot test.(Gumanti et al. 2020).

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Normality test

The normality test used One Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov using a significance level of 0.05. In the test results obtained a significance value of 0.2, which means the data has been normally distributed.

Table 1. One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		22
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	.23639845
	Most Extreme Differences	
	Absolute	.102
	Positive	.102
	Negative	-.086
Test Statistic		.102
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}

- a. Test distribution is Normal.
- b. Calculated from data.
- c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.
- d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

Classic Assumption Testing

Multicollinearity Testing

Multicollinearity testing aims to test whether the regression model finds a correlation between independent variables, which if there is no correlation between independent variables, the better the regression model will be. In the test, the VIF and tolerance values were 1.017 and 0.983, respectively, which means that the data does not have multicollinearity symptoms with reference:

Tolerance value <0.01 or VIF> 10 = multicollinearity occurs.
 Tolerance value > 0.01 or VIF <10 = no multicollinearity occurred

Table 2. Coefficients^a

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)		
Log_X1	.983	1.017
Log_X2	.983	1.017

a. Dependent Variable: Log Y

Autocorrelation Testing

The autocorrelation test aims to test whether in the linear regression model there is a correlation between confounding error in period t and confounding error in period t-1 (previous). This autocorrelation arises because the residual (confounding error) is not independent from one observation to another. This is often found in time series data. Autocorrelation testing using the Watson Durbin value. From the Watson Durbin test, the Watson Durbin value was 1.973.

Table 3. Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.903 ^a	.815	.795	.24853	1.973

a. Predictors: (Constant), Cash Flow, EPS
 b. Dependent Variable: Stock Prices

Watson's Durbin value is said to have no autocorrelation symptoms if $Du < DW < (4 - Du)$. So that from the value that has been obtained from the test it can be said that the data does not have autocorrelation symptoms.

Heteroscedasticity Testing

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in the regression model there is an inequality of variance from the residuals of one observation to another. A good regression model is that there is no heteroscedasticity. Most of the cross-sectional data contain heterosexuality situations because they collect data that represent multiple sizes. For this reason, testing using the Scatterplot is carried out

Figure 1. Scatterplot

Judging from the Scatterplot test, the results are as shown in the Figure above. The spread of plots on the Scatterplot results is said to be normal if they do not form a certain pattern but spread without a certain pattern. From the results above, it shows that the distribution of plots is spreading without forming a pattern so that it can be said that the data does not have heteroscedasticity symptoms

Table 4. Effect of Earning Per Share on Stock Prices Coefficients^a

Model	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	2.318	.032		
EPS	8.238	.000	.983	1.017
Cash Flow	2.855	.010	.983	1.017

a. Dependent Variable: Stock Prices

The significant column coefficient table shows the presence or absence of EPS influence on stock prices, where the significance level is 0.05 so that if the value > 0.05 can be said to have a significant effect. In this test, the significance value of variable X1 or EPS has a significance of 0.00, which means that H1 is accepted and H0 is rejected, EPS has a significant effect on stock prices.

The results of this test are supported by the results of previous research conducted by (Badruzaman 2017). In his research, testing was carried out using 31 data on chemical companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, the test results stated that earnings per share had a significant effect on stock prices. Likewise, research from (Setiawan and Tjun 2010) who conducted research on banks that had gone public in the 2007-2009 period stated the same thing.

Effect of Cash Flows from Operating Activities on Stock Prices

In regression testing, the data in the table above shows a significance value of $0.01 < 0.05$, which means that H1 is accepted and H0 is rejected, which means that cash flow from operating activities has a significant effect on stock prices.

After conducting the variable test on stock prices, it was found that there were differences in the test results in previous research conducted by (Setiawan and Tjun 2010) on banks listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in the 2007-2009 period which had research results that cash flow from operating activities was not has a significant effect on stock prices, these results do not support the results of this study.

The Adjusted R Square value in the model summary table shows the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. In this test, the value of Adjusted R Square is 0.795, this means that the change in stock price is influenced by earnings per share and operating cash flow is 79.5% and 20.5% is influenced by other factors.

5. CONCLUSION

The test results from this study obtained similarities and differences in previous studies. The test results of this study indicate that EPS and cash flow from operating activities have a significant effect on stock prices whereas in previous studies, EPS has a significant effect on stock prices in research conducted by (Badruzaman 2017; Setiawan and Tjun 2010). Meanwhile, (Setiawan and Tjun 2010) research had different results in testing operating cash flows on stock prices, namely the results of the study stated that operating cash flow had no effect on stock prices.

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